

ON AN INTER-SCALE MODEL FOR MATRIX FAILURES IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This article presents an inter-scale failure theory for matrix tensile failures that occur in laminate plies. The theory is based on two key postulations: one is the existence of a probabilistic tensile strength parameter between adjacent fibers; the other is related to the fiber-packing connectivity that affects matrix cracking. Both postulations need experimental correlation; for this, a test method is described. To apply the theory, detailed stress fields at the fiber-matrix scale must be recovered after the analysis of laminates under specific loading; then, matrix tensile cracks that occur in laminates can be simulated without further experimental correlation. For illustration purpose, a model composite system is used in two matrix-cracking cases: one is the 90°-compact tension specimen with or without a side-crack; the other is related to transverse cracking in cross-ply laminates under longitudinal tension; both problems are now classical; but a satisfactory model for the critical loads causing matrix cracking has not here-to-fore been available.

Keywords: Fiber-matrix and ply scales; ply homogenization and de-homogenization; ply matrix failures; an inter-scale failure theory.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical characterization of fiber-reinforced composites can be conducted at multiple characteristic length scales, depending on the composite system and the particular property to be extracted. For a class of structural laminates made of unidirectional tape (ply) systems, mechanical characterization typically begins at the fiber-matrix scale. By means of a homogenization procedure, the fibrous ply is represented by a homogeneous and anisotropic equivalent that is endowed with a set of effective properties [1-3]; multi-ply laminates are then treated as a two- or three-dimensional layered body, capable of carrying external load [4,5]. While this forward characterization routine greatly simplifies laminate design and analysis [6], ply homogenization disregards some important inter-scale effects stemming from interactions between elements at the fiber-matrix scale and those at the laminate ply scale. Such effects are especially pronounced in laminates where the ratio of ply-thickness to fiber diameter and that of laminate thickness to ply thickness are small.

Inter-scale effects manifest themselves profoundly in stress-wave motions, impact responses and crack initiation in laminates. For instance, the longitudinal and/or transverse strengths of unidirectional ply systems are not unique properties of the ply material; rather, they vary greatly depending on the manner in which the ply-specimen is tested: free-standing, adhered onto a substrate, or sandwiched with a core [7]. Many documented examples of varied ply strength include matrix cracking and delamination [8].

The general view is that localized microcracks occur even below the fiber-matrix scale; their growth and coalescence into higher length scale can be influenced by mutual interactions amongst material and/or

geometrical elements in both scales. Hence, in general, ply strength in laminates cannot be independently characterized without the inclusion of inter-scale effects [9].

There have been efforts to recover the complex stress fields at the fiber-matrix scale, after laminates are analyzed [10-12]. These efforts are made, in part, in the hope that some of the afore-mentioned inter-scale effects may be recovered and their influence on laminate failures examined. To do so, not only a recover routine is needed, but also a general ply failure theory that account for the inter-scale effects.

In a recent article [13], the authors examined some of the prevailing models for ply homogenization. The focus is placed on the representative volume elements (RVE) and their possible use in the recover routine, coined as de-homogenization. It is found that the single-fiber RVE is not consistent with the underlying assumptions (statistical homogeneity and material symmetry) even for homogenization; moreover, it cannot recover the inter-scale effects when used for de-homogenization.

In a sequel [14], the authors then presented a multi-fiber RVE. In order to justify the statistical material symmetry and homogeneity assumptions, especially for systems having a random fiber array, the volume of the RVE must be sufficiently large; furthermore, the interior region, known as the center-element, must be sufficiently away from the RVE boundary. Then, the stress field in the center-element is insensitive to the detailed conditions on the RVE boundary, as long as they are statically equivalent. In fact, the microfield in the center-element so computed will be exact or nearly exact. Thus, if the stresses and the strains in the center-element are used for homogenization, the effective property so rendered will be exact. Moreover, if the multi-fiber RVE is used for de-homogenization, the microfield inside the center-element so rendered is also exact, and the inter-scale effects are fully included therein.

In this article, the authors present a theory that uses the recovered stress field at the fiber-matrix scale to model intra-ply matrix cracking in laminates. The theory is of probabilistic and mechanistic in nature, but it needs only one correlative experiment to define the critical material parameters in the failure model. Two well-known matrix-cracking cases are simulated using the present theory: one is the 90°-compact tension specimen with or without a side-crack; the other is transverse cracking in cross-ply laminates under longitudinal tension. Both problems have not here-to-fore been modeled adequately by any existing ply failure theories.

Since most of the results are to be obtained numerically, a specific unidirectional ply system with known fiber and matrix properties will be used throughout.

AN INTER-SCALE FAILURE THEORY

The General Theory

Fig. 1 shows a unidirectional laminate specimen subject to a uniform tension σ_0 transverse to the fibers. In this case, the homogenized field is uniformly stressed by σ_0 ; and it is free of any residual stresses. The recovered microfield at the fiber-matrix scale, however, will contain self-equilibrated thermal residual stresses due to composite fabrication (characterized by ΔT), in addition to that induced by the applied far-field σ_0 . Both are non-uniform.

Let the exact fiber distribution be recognized at the fiber-matrix scale; a unit-pair of parallel fibers is then identified (see inset in Fig.1). Say, for the i th unit-pair, the stress between the two fibers is calculated: $\sigma_i = k_i \sigma_0 + \sigma_T$. Here, k_i is a magnification factor due to fiber-to-fiber interaction; and σ_T is the residual stress due to ΔT .

Fig. 1. Transverse tension applied to a unidirectional laminate; inset: a unit-pair and stress between fibers.

Now, tensile separation of any unit-pair, say the i th pair, will occur in-situ if the maximum tensile stress σ_i between the fibers exceeds the limit x . Here, x is the in-situ tensile strength of the unit-pair, a random variable with the probability function, $f(x)$. If $f(x)$ is known, the probability for the unit-pair to fail in-situ under the applied tension σ_0 is given by:

$$F_i(\sigma_0) = \int_0^{k_i \sigma_0 + \sigma_T} f(x) dx \quad (1)$$

Suppose that across the width of the specimen there are N connected unit-pairs; but tensile failure of any one unit-pair can initiate unstable crack propagation across the specimen. In this case, for the probability of specimen fracture under the applied σ_0 , the weakest-link model applies:

$$F_{sys}(\sigma_0) = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^N [1 - F_i(\sigma_0)] \quad (2)$$

In particular, if probability of specimen fracture is specified (e.g. the mean of F_{sys}), the critical σ_0 is found from (2).

The theory hinges on two postulations: namely, a tensile strength x exists between the two fibers in the unit-pair, and the connectivity of the unit-pairs is represented by a weakest-link in the event of specimen fracture. Obviously, these two postulations must be correlated with experiment; but this is not the focus here, as it will be left for a future endeavor. In what follows, an experiment is outlined for determining $f(x)$ of the unit-pair and for possible correlation of the weakest-link postulation.

A Suggested Experiment for $f(x)$.

Suppose a model unidirectional ply system is used to fabricate a sample of 90° -tension specimens. Here, the model ply system has the fibers packed in a square array. When the sample is tested to failure by the far-field tensile stress, σ_0 , in a manner as shown in Fig.1, the specimen fails as $\sigma_0 \rightarrow X$, the fracture

strength of the specimen. Let all the X values obtained from the sample be fitted to a three-parameter Weibull function:

$$F_{sys}(X) = 1 - \text{Exp}\{ -[(X - X_L)/\beta_o]^{\alpha_o} \} \quad (3)$$

In (3), X_L is the lower limit of X; α_o and β_o are the shape and scale parameters, respectively; all three are found by the fitting the sample data for X.

Now, in the specimen microfield, all unit-pairs are the same due to the assumed square fiber array. Hence, it is necessary only to recover the stresses in any one unit-pair through de-homogenization. In particular, the residual stress σ_T and the stress magnification factor k between the two fibers in the unit-pair are to be obtained.

Then, the failure probability function $f(x)$ of the unit-pair is inferred from using (2) and (3); this yields a Weibull function for $f(x)$, owing to the weakest-link postulation. The three parameters x_L , α and β are:

$$x_L = \sigma_T + kX_L \quad \alpha = \alpha_o \quad \beta = k\beta_o N^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

In (4), N is the number of unit-pairs across the width of the test specimen.

ILLUSTRATIVE APPLICATIONS

A unidirectional E-glass/epoxy ply system having a square fiber array is used in all applications. Fiber and matrix are linearly elastic with the following properties:

$$\begin{array}{llll} E_f = 73 \text{ GPa} & \nu_f = 0.22 & \alpha_f = 5.04 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C} & \text{fiber diam.} = 10.2 \mu\text{m} \\ E_m = 3.5 \text{ GPa} & \nu_m = 0.35 & \alpha_m = 58 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C} & V_f = 0.5 \end{array}$$

The system's cure temperature is 178 °C; but the residual stresses in post-cured laminates are evaluated at the uniform temperature difference $\Delta T = -111$ °C, owing to post-cure stress relaxation.

Homogenization of the ply system is carried out using a 9-fiber RVE, with the center element containing a single fiber only [14]; the ply is then a three-dimensional homogeneous solid with square symmetry and the thermo-elastic constants are obtained as:

$$\begin{array}{llll} E_{LL} = 38.2 \text{ GPa} & E_{TT} = 11 \text{ GPa} & G_{LT} = 3.36 \text{ GPa} & G_{TT} = 2.61 \text{ GPa} \\ \nu_{LT} = 0.28 & \nu_{TT} = 0.38 & \alpha_{LL} = 7.8 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C} & \alpha_{TT} = 35.6 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C} \end{array}$$

In de-homogenization, the recovered self-equilibrated residual stress field is computed using the same 9-fiber RVE. In particular, the residual stress between the two fibers in the unit-pair is: $\sigma_T = -18$ MPa.

Characterization of $f(x)$.

Ideally, if a sample of the 90°-tension specimens could be fabricated using the model glass/epoxy ply system as described above, then, testing the sample to failure would provide the needed X data for determining $f(x)$ of the unit-pair. Moreover, if samples of the 90° specimens could be made with a range of different widths, then the collective {X} sample data could be used to correlate the weakest-link postulation. However, such pertinent data is unavailable at this point; a search in the open literature for comparable data is conducted. It seems that most strength tests on glass-epoxy systems give similar

values for the transverse ply strength, even if they are made from different epoxy systems and varied fiber volume contents. Thus, for purpose of illustration, a hypothetical yet realistic function for $F_{sys}(X)$ for the 90°-tension specimen is assumed here. In addition, for definiteness, let there be 250 connected unit-pairs across the width of the specimen.

Let $F_{sys}(X)$ be a Weibull function, with the parameters $X_L=13.8$ MPa, $\alpha_o=10$ and $\beta_o= 48.3$ MPa; and the mean is 60 MPa. These values are within the range found in most glass/epoxy systems.

The above is finally used to determine the probability failure function $f(x)$ for the unit-pair. As outlined earlier, the microfield due to ΔT ($=-111$ °C) and the applied σ_o are computed through de-homogenization. Here, for each and every unit-pair, $\sigma_T=-18$ MPa and the stress magnification factor $k=1.714$. The function $f(x)$ is rendered a Weibull function, with the parameters calculated from (4):

$$\alpha = 10; \quad \beta = 143 \text{ MPa}; \quad x_L = 5.7 \text{ MPa}.$$

Application-I: The Compact Tension Test.

Consider the 90°-compact tension specimen with a side-crack, Fig. 2. Let it be tested to fracture under the tensile strain ϵ_o . Traditionally, the critical strain $(\epsilon_o)_{cr}$ at specimen fracture is used to determine the critical stress intensity factor K_{Ic} or the critical strain energy release rate G_{Ic} of the homogenized composite; of course, the correlative fracture analysis is conducted at the macroscale. It is well known that fracture mechanics correlates well when the side-crack is sufficiently large; otherwise, a constant K_{Ic} or G_{Ic} cannot be obtained.

By means of the inter-scale theory just outlined above, the compact tension test can be simulated completely, if the function $f(x)$ of the unit-pair is determined a priori. In this case, the stress field in the homogenized specimen due to the applied ϵ_o is first obtained, including the singular field near the crack-tip (the residual stress state is null); by de-homogenization, the stress fields at the fiber-matrix scale due to ΔT and the applied ϵ_o are recovered. Here, the multi-fiber RVE used contains 80 fibers as schematically shown in Fig. 2; the center-element contains the crack-line from the side-crack tip to a length of 8 unit-pairs, see inset in Fig. 2. The stresses and strains on the RVE boundary are drawn from the macroscale analysis, while the stresses in the RVE are computed through a microscale analysis based on a generalized plain strain finite-element routine. The residual stress σ_T and the magnification factor k for each of the unit-pairs along the crack-line are obtained.

Fig. 2. The 90° compact tension specimen with side-crack a_{ck} . Inset: the multi-fiber RVE and unit pairs along the crack-line.

Fig. 3 displays the tensile stress σ (normalized by $\sigma_0 = \varepsilon_0 E_{TT}$), along the crack-line for the specimen with $a_{ck} = 10a_0$; here, a_0 is the side of the square area that contains one fiber; in this model system, $a_0 = 12.8 \mu\text{m}$. The solid curve is the tensile stress distribution calculated at the microscale; the waviness of the curve reflects stress magnification due to fiber interaction in the unit-pair; thus, the magnification factor k for each unit-pair is calculated. The wavy stress distribution is intensified by the side-crack as well, as the k factor is the largest in the unit-pair next to the crack-tip. The dotted curve is the corresponding stress distribution calculated at the macroscale. Both the microscale and macroscale curves are singular at the crack-tip; but the intensity in the former is weaker than the latter.

As for the residual stress σ_T distribution along the crack-line, it is null at the macroscale but is nontrivial at the microscale; the latter is not shown due to length limitation imposed on this article.

Fig. 3. Tensile stress distribution due to the applied σ_0 along the crack-line

For the compact tension specimen with known side-crack and tested under the applied ε_0 , the probability of failure F_{sys} is then calculated from (2). Conversely, if a value for F_{sys} is specified, the critical applied strain $(\varepsilon_0)_{cr}$ at specimen fracture is also calculated from (2).

Fig. 4. Critical applied stress $(\varepsilon_0)_{cr}$ versus side-crack size.

Fig. 4 shows the computed $(\epsilon_o)_{cr}$ versus the side-crack a_{ck} relation rendered by the inter-scale theory and by fracture analysis. The solid curve is computed for $F_{sys} = 0.632$, while the dashed curve is computed using $K_{Ic} = 0.6 \text{ MPa(m)}^{0.5}$ (or $G_{Ic} = 119 \text{ J/m}^2$), a commonly found value for most epoxy-based systems.

It is seen that the inter-scale failure theory provides a finite value for $(\epsilon_o)_{cr}$ at any a_{ck} size: large, small or null; the trend of the curve follows that found experimentally. On the other hand, $(\epsilon_o)_{cr}$ rendered by fracture analysis is unbounded when a_{ck} is small. The two curves agree however, when a_{ck} is large; in this case, a_{ck} should be larger than $10a_o$.

Application II: Transverse Cracking in Cross-Ply Laminates.

A cross-plyed laminates under the longitudinal tensile strain ϵ_o is schematically shown in Fig. 5. Here, the thickness of the outside 0° layers is kept constant, while the thickness of the 90° layer varies. When the applied strain ϵ_o reaches a certain value, one or more transverse cracks can occur in the 90° layer; there can be more cracks if the applied laminate strain continues to increase, until all cracks are formed giving rise to a characteristic spacing. Both the critical strain at the onset of the first few cracks and the final characteristic crack spacing can vary with the thickness of the 90° layer, indicating that cracking of the 90° layer is affected by inter-scale effects. This problem and related ones have been extensively studied in more than 20 years, but most of the modeling approaches have not been satisfactory (see [9] for a review).

Fig.5. Schematics of a cross-plyed laminate under uniaxial tension.
Inset: RVE used for de-homogenization

Early in the mid 1980's, a heuristic yet physical *effective flaw* postulation was used to treat this problem [15]. The postulation stipulates that the 90° layer possesses materially a distribution of effective flaws that can act like small cracks when the 90-layer is stressed. That is, when the in-situ stress or strain in the layer reaches a critical value, one or more of the hypothetical flaws will propagate into transverse cracks seen at the ply scale. Given the size of the largest effective flaws and the fracture toughness of the 90° layer, the critical in-situ ply stress or ply strain at the onset of transverse cracking is determined via fracture analysis. This approach could also facilitate a stochastic/mechanistic analysis for subsequent cracks in the 90° layer under increasing laminate load; the latter can mimic the observed characteristic crack spacing as well, see [15].

The difficulty in the effective flaw postulation is the characterization of the effective flaws, their size and location distributions in the given ply system. Furthermore, the distributions must vary with the 90° layer thickness if the thickness-dependent trend seen in experiments is to be captured by the analysis. To some extent, the effective flaw approach reflects some of the inter-scale effects; but to this date, the postulation remains without a validation.

Actually, transverse cracking in cross-plyed laminates can now be treated by the inter-scale failure theory, provided the function $f(x)$ of the 90° unit-pair is characterized a priori. As a specific example case study, let the thickness of the 0° layer be equal to $20a_0$ while the thickness of the 90° layer varies from $4a_0$ to $80a_0$. Through de-homogenization (see inset in Fig. 5 for the RVE used), the microfield in the laminate is recovered; and in particular, the in-situ residual stress σ_T and the stress magnification factor k in the local unit-pairs are obtained.

It is noted that the k factors computed for the unit-pairs across the thickness of the 90° layer are not uniform; it depends on the distance of the unit-pair to the $90^\circ/0^\circ$ layer-interface. For instance, for the laminate with 90° layer thickness of $4a_0$, the unit-pair next to the 0° layer has $k=1.68$; for the laminate with 90° layer thickness of $80a_0$, the unit-pair located in the middle of the thickness has $k=1.714$. The slightly variation is due to the 0° layer constraining effect; in general, the stiffer the 0° layer, the more pronounced the constraining effect. In the present case, E_{LL} is only 3.4 times stiffer than E_{TT} .

The residual stress σ_T in the unit-pairs also varies with the 90° layer thickness. For instance, in the case where the 90° layer thickness is $4a_0$, $\sigma_T=38.6$ MPa; if it is $80a_0$, $\sigma_T=23.4$ MPa. This is obviously due to the difference in the thermal expansion coefficients between the 0° and the 90° layers.

By the inter-scale failure theory, as before, onset of transverse cracking in the 90° layer occurs when the in-situ stress in a unit-pair reaches the in-situ strength x . In this case, since there are N unit-pair connected in series, the probability that the series fails is synonymous to onset of transverse cracking. Thus, the probability for the onset of transverse crack under the applied laminate strain $\varepsilon_o(=E_{TT}\sigma_o)$ is calculated from (1) and (2). Fig. 6 shows the critical laminate tensile strain $(\varepsilon_o)_{cr}$ at the onset of transverse cracking versus the 90° layer thickness, for the failure probability $F_{sys}=0.632$. The $(\varepsilon_o)_{cr}$ versus 90° layer thickness relation has the same trend as that found in numerous previous experiments. Furthermore, the values of $(\varepsilon_o)_{cr}$ are also within the range found in laminates made of epoxy-based systems.

Fig. 6. Critical laminate strain at onset of transverse cracking vs. 90° layer thickness

Finally, the results shown in Fig. 6 may be used to correlate the effective flaw postulation, discussed previously. Fig. 7 shows a family of three parametric curves (solid curves) for laminates having 90° layer thickness of $20a_0$, $40a_0$ and $80a_0$, respectively. These curves are generated by fracture analysis using $G_{Ic}=119 \text{ J/m}^2$ and treating the effective flaw size, a_e as a free parameter. If the critical laminate strain at onset of transverse cracking so predicted is to match that found by the inter-scale failure theory, the effective flaw size a_e can thus be determined by correlating the results in Fig. 6 with the respective curve in Fig. 7. For the three laminates considered: $a_e = 3.9a_0$, $6.4a_0$ and $7.4a_0$, respectively.

Again, these a_{ck} values are in the range assumed in previous studies reported in the open literature (see [15]).

Fig.7. Correlation of the inter-scale and ply-scale solutions to define the effective flaw size.

CONCLUDING REMARK

The inter-scale failure theory presented herein is, possibly, the first attempt to use the recovered stress fields at the fiber-matrix scale to simulate matrix cracks that occur at the ply scale in laminates. Although the theory and its underlying postulations have yet to be experimentally correlated, its utility seems to be promising in review of the application examples presented alongside. If the theory can ever be validated by controlled experiments, such as suggested in this article, it could have a far-reaching implication on the fundamental premise of the ply failure theories still in use in the field.

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